

Data Management Plan for Academy of Finland September 2016 call

Title of proposal: *Reshaping cellulose: nano and micro beads through molecular self-assembly*

Applicant: Ilkka Kilpeläinen, Professor, Laboratory of Organic Chemistry, Department of Chemistry, University of Helsinki

Date: September 2016

Description:

The current proposal seeks for novel methods to replace synthetic polymers in microplastics (nano and micro particles) with environmentally friendly cellulosic materials. We suggest two epoch-making methods for cellulose regeneration: cellulose is shown to micro phase separate from its solution in ionic liquids 1) upon cooling and 2) when transferred from ionic liquid to aqueous media. Both processes result in formation of spherical beads of varying morphology. The beads can be chemically modified to obtain biodegradable benign materials with designed properties.

1. COLLABORATORS (ARCHIVES, STORAGE SERVICE ETC.)

With which collaborators will the data be managed and made openly available?

The data collected during the project will be managed and stored using the services provided or recommended by the University Helsinki IT Center.

Experimental data will be published as supplementary files according the publication plan.

After completion of this research project, the appropriate data will be deposited to the open repository provided by the University of Helsinki (under development) or Zenodo; EUDAT etc. repositories which enable open access to the data via a persistent identifier.

2. TYPE OF DATA

What type of data (e.g. qualitative, quantitative, measurements) will the project collect or use?
The data content is described in more detail in the research plan.

Data for R&D process includes description of the synthesis and sample preparation, basic characterization of products at each step, studies on polymers in solution, preparation of the cellulose-based materials (e.g. beads), studies on their physical properties and analysis and further modification of the materials. Data for qualitative and quantitative analysis of samples will be used to loop the whole R&D process in order to produce materials of our interest.

3. TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION

How will the data be documented? For example, what file format and metadata standard will be used?

We will collect and store information on used chemicals, procedures, samples preparation methods, raw data files from experiments and results of analysis (NMR, FTIR, light scattering, rheology, optical and electron microscopy etc.) in notebooks and as electronic measurements files. Each batch of synthesized materials will be labelled and stored in the designated places. All results

will first be added to the laboratory notebooks. The records collected using instruments will be electronically backed up: stored by the researchers, archived on external hard discs and backed-up on the group storage space of the University of Helsinki or Zenodo. The data for preserving and sharing will be converted to standard open formats (pdf/a, tiff, etc.) and provided with appropriate metadata according to the instructions of the repository. For networked resources, we will use DDI specification, which is usually written in XML format. Supplementary files will be published using PDF or MS Office formats depending on the journal requirements. In case of video format, MPEG-4 (.mp4) will be used.

4. ETHICS AND LEGAL COMPLIANCE

How will ethical issues concerning data management (e.g. sensitive personal information, third-party access to data) be taken into account? Please note that the ethical issues that concern data collection and research implementation are described in the research plan.

We follow the Guidelines of Responsible Conduct of Research drawn up by the National Advisory Board on Research Integrity. No sensitive personal information will be produced in this project.

How will copyright and IPR issues be managed?

The members of the research team will decide and agree on the tasks, responsibilities and rights relating to data collection, data processing and use.

Collection, storing and management of data will be performed in accordance with the Academy of Finland Guidelines, the University of Helsinki Research Data Policy and Terms of Use and Privacy Policies for IT Services.

We stand for making all produced data and results openly available where possible. The research data meant for reuse will be available under CC-BY licence.

5. DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

How will the data be made available for subsequent use by other researchers?

Results of project will be disseminated by publication in scholarly journals as openly as possible. Supplementary data will be as detailed as possible including sufficient metadata.

The access to raw experimental data will be regulated by PI and can be provided in open format followed with metadata to enable re-use.

After completion of this research project, the appropriate data can be deposited to the most suitable open repository.